

Laboratory scale treatability study of industrial waste water – Leather chemicals and kraft paper industry

D. C. Mukherjee^{a*}, S. B. Chowdhury^b, A. Paul^b and Paulomi Das^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry and Environment, Heritage Institute of Technology, Anandpur,
Kolkata-700 107, India

^bEnvirocheck, 189 & 190, Rastraguru Avenue, Kolkata-700 028, India

E-mail : envcheck@cal2.vsnl.net.in

Manuscript received 15 March 2011, accepted 19 May 2011

Abstract : Due to industrialization a number of different industries have become interested to invest in our country. Some of the industries are discharging their waste water without treatment to the water bodies causing ecological imbalance in aquatic life as a whole. In this study water samples were collected from two industries, manufacturing leather chemicals and kraft paper. A laboratory scale treatability study was conducted to find out an appropriate treatment procedure to achieve a depletion of pollutants – BOD and COD to a level to meet the standard for discharge to surface water bodies. The treatment procedure was standardized and a physicochemical treatment followed by biological treatment and tertiary treatment was found to be more suitable. The dosing rate of chemicals and retention period of biological degradation were fixed. On the basis of the findings the design criteria of individual units of effluent treatment plant was finalized.

Keywords : Pollution, waste water, chemical, biological, leather chemicals, kraft paper.

Introduction

Environmental pollution has been a major matter of concern for industrial development. The industrial and technological progress however, has created negative impact on the environment in terms of its pollution and degradation. With the growth of industry over the past century, toxic chemicals have become a part of our daily lives. The industrial pollution due to its nature has the potential to cause irreversible reactions in the environment and hence is posing a major threat to our very existence. Unplanned and haphazard industrialization has substantially increased the risk to the environment. The carrying capacity of the environment is not unlimited and some areas or ecosystem are more susceptible to adverse environmental impacts. The growing world population and industrialization has focused concerns on the implications of water pollution and also on the threat to water supplies from industrial accidents. Leather industry has been categorized as one of the high polluting industries. Leather making activity can have adverse impact on the environment¹. Leather industry contributes to one of the major industrial pollution problems facing the country,

and the pollution causing chemicals, viz. lime, sodium sulphide, salt, solvents, etc. arise mainly from of leather processing^{2,3}. With the urbanization the demand of packaging materials also has grown rapidly. Kraft paper is required for packaging of different consumer items, engineering items etc. Keeping in view the increase in demand the paper mill has taken project for manufacturing Kraft Paper. Along with leather industry, the production and use of paper has a number of adverse effects on the environment. The used process water from a paper mill contains a lot of organic materials resulting in high biological oxygen demand (BOD) and dissolved organic carbon (DOC) and other chemicals⁴. Only few industries have their own treatment plant for checking the effects on environment. Many factories discharge their effluent into nearest land or river through sewers. This process may alter the physical and chemical composition of environment. Due to this increment it is essential to find out an effective treatment of waste waters as well as for pollution control and treatment must be effective and economic.

The aim and objectives of the study was (i) to detect the characters of waste water effluents of two different

industries, (ii) to elucidate the efficiency of treatment process including physical, chemical, biological and tertiary treatment and (iii) to find out % depletion of pollutants in effluents after treatment.

Materials and method :

This study was carried out on mixed waste water collected from leather chemical effluent and paper mill effluent. At first, pH, TSS, COD, BOD of mixed waste water were measured for both. Phenolic compound was also estimated in case of leather manufacturing company. The same parameters were measured after treatment. The instrument used in the experiment was Jar Test Apparatus, D.O. Meter, Spectrophotometer, COD Digester, pH meter, Pilot scale plant etc.

In this study the treatment process involved physical, chemical, biological and tertiary treatment process⁵. The chemicals used in treatments are given below.

Chemicals used : (1) Lime solution (10%), (2) alum solution (10%), (3) non-ionic poly electrolyte solution (0.1%) (for only paper manufacturing), (4) KMnO₄ (for only leather manufacturing) and (5) activated carbon.

Principle of treatment :

(I) Manufacturing of leather chemicals :

(A) Chemical treatment :

Precipitation by acidification – Heavy precipitation and significant removal of pollutants were carried out with addition of concentrated H₂SO₄.

Chemical oxidization by KMnO₄ – Chemical oxidization in waste water treatment typically involved the use of the oxidizing agent such as potassium permanganate to bring about change in the chemical composition of a compound or a group of compound. The use of this chemical oxidization was for the reduction of COD and BOD, oxidization of ammonia and the oxidization of non biodegradable organic compounds.

Half reaction :

Precipitation by lime and alum – Lime was added for maintaining the alkalinity required to react with alum as well as to increase the pH value. Then alum was added to water in the presence of alkalinity, which produced aluminum hydroxide as gelatinous floc, that settled slowly through the waste water and swept out the suspended

solid as well as reduced the level of COD and BOD and finally neutralization of waste water.

When lime alone was added as a precipitant the principles of clarification may be explained by the following reactions.

A sufficient quantity of lime must therefore be added to combine with all the free carbonic acid and with the carbonic acid of the bicarbonates (half bound carbonic acid) to produce calcium carbonate, which acts as the coagulant.

When alum was added to waste water containing calcium and magnesium bicarbonate alkalinity, the reaction that occurs may be illustrated as below.

The insoluble aluminum hydroxide was a gelatinous floc that settled slowly through the waste water, swept out suspended material and producing other changes.

(B) Microbiological treatment :

Two stages, activated sludge process – As the effluent was biodegradable, biological treatment was required to remove biodegradable load. Aeration was used for transferring oxygen to biological treatment process. Under proper pH 7.0 to 8.0 the biodegradable organic substance of waste water was completely degraded by biological oxidization, part of it was oxidized while rest was converted into biological mass in the biological reactor. The end product of the metabolism was either low molecular weight gas or liquid. There was a third stage of microbiological treatment to reduce the BOD load as was depicted in the treatability study. For this a fluidized bed bio-pack media was envisaged.

Aerobic attached growth treatment processes – Aerobic attached growth biological treatment processes were used to remove organic matter found in waste water. The attached growth process included the trickling filter, fluidized bed reactor, the roughing filter, rotating biological contactor. Fluidized bed reactor was considered for this Effluent Treatment Plant.

(C) Tertiary treatment :

The tertiary treatment through activated carbon ab-

sorption was applied to remove remaining organic compounds as well as odour of effluent.

Maturation pond :

Maturation or low rate stabilization ponds were constructed to provide for secondary effluent polishing and seasonal nitrification. The biological mechanisms involved were similar to other aerobic suspended growth processes. Operationally, the residual biological solids were endogenously respired and ammonia was converted to nitrate using the oxygen supplied from surface re-aeration and from algae. A detention time of 18 to 20 days has been suggested as the minimum period required to provide for complete endogenous respiration of the residual solids.

Systems description :

The effluent water generation source is mainly from kettle washing process. Floating organic material was separated from the mixed effluent. The effluent was taken in flash mixing Tank No. 1 (Fig. 1), where H₂SO₄ was added. From the flash mixing Tank No. 1, the effluent was brought to the first primary settling Tank No. 1 where the precipitated sludge was settled at the bottom and the overflow water was brought to flash mixing Tank No. 2 where appropriate quantity of KMnO₄ solution was added for oxidation before entering into primary settling Tank No. 2 where further precipitation was occurred. The overflow water was fed to the flash mixing Tank No. 3 to maintain the alkalinity and subsequently to the flash mixing Tank No. 4 where coagulation was occurred. The overflow from the flash mixing Tank No. 4 was then brought to the primary settling Tank No. 3 where the precipitation of the coagulated mass took place. The precipitate was settled at the bottom of the tank as sludge, which along with sludge from the other two primary settling tanks was brought to a sludge drying bed either by gravity or through a pressure filtration unit.

The clear liquid from the primary settling Tank No. 3 was brought to a holding Tank No. 1 from where continuous feeding of effluent was done round the clock to 1st aeration tank where two days of aerobic biodegradation of biodegradable organic part of the effluent occurred. From 1st aeration tank the overflow was brought to 1st secondary settling tank, where biological mass was settled at the bottom of the tank. A part of sludge (biomass) was recycled by a sludge pump back to the aeration tank for

recycling and other part was brought to sludge drying bed. Then the overflow from 1st secondary settling tank was brought to 2nd aeration tank where two days of aerobic biodegradation was occurred to degrade biodegradable organic part of effluent. After this the liquid was transferred to 2nd secondary settling tank and one part of sludge was recycled to 2nd aeration tank to maintain the desired MLSS.

The clear liquid from 2nd secondary settling tank was brought to the Biopac media reactor to remove the remaining organic matter. The clear effluent after Biopac system was stored in the holding Tank No. 2 from where the clear water was fed to activated carbon bed to remove bioorganic pollutant as well as color and odor.

After activated carbon bed the effluent water was stored in a simulated maturation pond for natural removal of residual pollutants. The following technical details have been calculated on the basis of twelve (12) hours of chemical treatment followed by twenty four (24) hours of biological treatment. The schematic diagram is given in Fig. 1.

(II) Production of kraft paper :

(A) First stage – physical treatment :

The first stage in waste water treatment was the removal of the coarse solids. The usual procedure was to pass the raw waste water through coarse screen. Here screen was cleaned manually.

(B) Second stage – chemical treatment :

In this stage lime was used for maintaining the alkalinity required to react with alum as well as to increasing the pH value. Then alum was added to water in the presence of alkalinity which produce aluminum hydroxide gelatinous floc, that settled slowly through the waste water and swept out the suspended solid as well as reduction of COD and BOD.

After addition of lime as alkali and alum as coagulant a rapid mixing 1 to 3 min followed by flocculation with addition of non-ionic polyelectrolyte used as coagulant aid. Here non-ionic polyelectrolyte which adsorbed and flocculated by hydrogen bonding between the suspended solid particle and the polar group in the polymer, resulted rapid reduction and settling of suspended particle.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of treatment plant for leather chemical effluent.

(C) Third stage – biological treatment :

As the effluent was biodegradable so, biological treatment was required to remove biodegradable load. Aeration was used for transferring oxygen to biological treatment process. Under proper pH 7.0 to 8.0 the biodegradable organic substance of waste water were completely destroyed by biological oxidization, part of it's was oxidized while rest were converted into biological mass in the biological reactor. The end product of the metabolism were either low molecular weight gas or liquid.

Systems description :

On the basis of the treatability study an appropriate system is planned. The effluent water was generated mainly from the manufacturing process. This effluent will be brought to equalization tank after passing through a screen. From the equalization the effluent was lifted to flash mixing Tank No. 1, where lime solution will be added to increase the alkalinity. From the flash mixing Tank No. 1 the effluent will be brought to flash mixing Tank No. 2 where appropriate quantity of alum solution will be added for coagulation before entering into slow mixing Tank No. 3 where non-ionic polyelectrolyte solution will be added to enhance the coagulation. The effluent from this tank will then be brought to primary settling tank where

the precipitation of the coagulated mass will occur. The precipitate will be settled at the bottom of the tank as sludge which will be brought to sludge drying bed by gravity. The clear liquid from the primary settling tank was brought to aeration tank where aerobic biodegradation of biodegradable organic part of the effluent will occur. From aeration tank the effluent will overflow to a secondary settling tank, where biological mass will settle at the bottom of the tank. A part of sludge will be recycled by a sludge pump back to the aeration tank for recycling and other part will be brought to sludge drying bed. The clear liquid from the secondary settling tank will be discharged to agricultural land. The schematic diagram is given in Fig. 1A.

Results and discussion

The manufacturing processes for leather tanning and paper require considerable quantities of waste water to be discharged to the sewer and irrigation channel. These effluents are characterized by high COD and BOD^{6,7}. Tables 1 and 1A show the water quality of the mixed waste used for the treatment for two industries. Changes in the process parameters after treatment are depicted in Tables 2 and 2A. (%) Depletion of pollutants in different steps are given in Tables 3 and 3A.

Fig. 1A. Schematic diagram of treatment plant for paper mill effluent.

Table 1. Characteristics of mixed effluent before treatment for leather chemical mfg. unit

pH	8.88
TSS (mg/L)	12280
COD (mg/L)	147260
BOD (mg/L)	60205
Phenolic compound (mg/L)	260

Table 1A. Characteristics of mixed effluent before treatment for paper mill effluent

pH	5.5
TSS (mg/L)	2800
COD (mg/L)	4500
BOD (mg/L)	1620

Chemical treatment :

However some form of pretreatment such as screening, pH adjustment is necessary, whether the discharge is to the municipal treatment works or to a water course⁸. In the present study an attempt had been made for leather industry by applying the oxidizing agent such as potassium permanganate to bring about change in the chemical composition of the liquid followed by chemical coagulant alum in the presence of alkali, as a pretreatment which produced aluminum hydroxide as gelatinous floc that settled slowly through the waste water and swept out the suspended solid. This treatment reduced the level of COD and BOD and finally neutralization of waste water.

Table 2. Characteristics of mixed effluent after treatment for leather chemical effluent

Water sample	pH	TSS (mg/L)	COD (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	Phenol (mg/L)
(A) After chemical treatment ^a	7.2	120	6143	2050	3.7
(B) After 1st stage of two days biological treatment	7.5	95	2450	800	2.0
(C) After 2nd stage of one day biological treatment	7.25	25	1000	280	1.2
(D) After Biopac media reactor	7.20	12	300	80	0.8
(E) Activated carbon bed	7.10	7	210	45	0.5
(F) After maturation pond (optional)	7.05	30	120	25	0.2

Volume of waste water taken in batch – 1000 ml.

^a10 ml conc. 36 (N) H₂SO₄ (30 min) at pH 3.0–4.0

supernatant + 63 g KMnO₄ (2 h)

supernatant + 25 ml 20% lime (30 min)

supernatant + 35 ml 20% alum at pH 7.5 per liter of effluent.

Table 2A. Characteristics of mixed effluent after treatment for paper mill effluent

Water sample	pH	TSS (mg/L)	COD (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)
(A) After physical separation	5.5	2464	4050	1555
(B) After chemical treatment	7.5	123	1215	545
(C) After biological treatment	7.2	60	120.0	55

Table 3. (%) Depletion of pollutants in different steps for leather chemical effluent

Water sample	TSS (%)	COD (%)	BOD (%)	Phenol (%)
(A) Chemical treatment	99.02	95.82	96.59	98.57
(B) After 1st stage of two days biological treatment	0.20	2.50	2.070	0.65
(C) After 2nd stage of one day biological treatment	0.57	0.98	0.86	0.30
(D) After Biopac media reactor	0.10	0.47	0.33	0.15
(E) Activated carbon bed	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.11
(F) After maturation pond (optional)	(-)0.18	0.06	0.03	0.11
Total reduction of pollutants for the total treatment process	99.75	99.89	99.93	99.89

Table 3A. (%) Depletion of pollutants in different steps for paper mill effluent

Water sample	TSS (%)	COD (%)	BOD (%)
(A) After physical separation	12	10	4.0
(B) After chemical treatment	83.64	63	62.34
(C) After biological treatment	2.25	24.33	30.24
Total reduction of pollutants for the total treatment process	97.89	97.33	96.59

After addition of lime as alkali and alum, non-ionic polyelectrolyte used as flocculant aid in case of paper effluent. Here non-ionic polyelectrolyte which adsorbed and flocculated by hydrogen bonding between the suspended solid particle and the polar group in the polymer, resulted rapid reduction and settling of suspended particle⁸. So, finally these enhanced the precipitation i.e. settling process and ultimate reduced the level of COD and BOD.

Fig. 2. Showing differences of TSS values before and after treatment for leather chemical effluent.

Fig. 2A. Showing differences of TSS values before and after treatment for paper mill effluent.

Stepwise reduction of levels of COD and BOD and rapid reduction after addition of non-ionic polyelectrolyte in paper effluent are discussed below. From the results (System-I), (Table 3B), it was seen that if only lime was added then the reduction in pollutants load could not be obtained more than 50%. Moreover due to slow sludge settling rate (500 ml sludge/liter of effluent in 30 min) this system was not accepted. In this system (System-II), (Table 3C), 0.1% non-ionic polyelectrolyte solution in varying quantity was added to 1 L of solution. It was

Table 3B. (%) Depletion of pollutants after addition of lime for paper mill effluent (System-I)

No.	Volume of lime solution (ml)	Reduction of TSS (%)	Reduction of COD (%)
1.	4	40	30
2.	6	52	38
3.	8	60	45
4.	10	65	48

Table 3C. (%) Depletion of pollutants after addition of polyelectrolyte for paper mill effluent (System-II)

No.	Volume of polyelectrolyte solution (ml)	Reduction of TSS (%)	Reduction of COD (%)
1.	0.5	30	24
2.	1.0	50	38
3.	1.5	50	38
4.	2	52	40

Fig. 3. Showing differences of COD values before and after treatment for leather chemical effluent.

noticed that there was no significant impact if more than 1.5 ml of this solution is added. The reduction of COD and TSS was not of significance. It was also observed that 1 ml of polyelectrolyte solution was enough for achiev-

Fig. 3A. Showing differences of COD values before and after treatment for paper mill effluent.

ing the reduction. As target was to reduce the pollutant's load as maximum as possible before allowing it to aeration tank, so the System-II was not be adequate to reduce the load by more than 50% though it had high sludge settling rate. In this System-III, (Tables 3D and 3E), the addition of polyelectrolyte solution was being done with varying quantity of lime solution. It was observed that settling of sludge was slow when pH was maintained at 10 but depletion of pollutant's load was satisfactory. But at final pH 10, it would not be possible to allow this treated effluent to activated sludge process. To achieve the expected performance in activated sludge process, the pH of the influent should be kept at pH 7.0 to 8.0. In the

Table 3D. (%) Depletion of pollutants after addition of lime and polyelectrolyte for paper mill effluent (System-III)

No.	Volume of lime solution (ml)	Volume of polyelectrolyte solution (ml)	pH	Reduction (%)	
				TSS	COD
1.	3	1	7.0	50	45
2.	6	1	8.5	75	56
3.	8.5	1	10.0	80	56

Table 3E. Settled sludge volume in different times after addition of lime and polyelectrolyte for paper mill effluent (System-III)

No.	System	Settled sludge volume in different times (ml)				
		2 min	5 min	10 min	15 min	30 min
1.	1 L sample + 3 ml lime + 1 ml polyelectrolyte	700	600	500	450	400
2.	1 L sample + 6 ml lime + 1 ml polyelectrolyte	600	500	400	300	300
3.	1 L sample + 8.5 ml lime + 1 ml polyelectrolyte	500	400	350	300	300

System-IV, (Tables 3F and 3G), lime and alum both were added. First the lime solution was added to raise the pH 8 to 10 for increasing alkalinity and then by adding the alum the pH of the solution was brought down to 6.5 to

Table 3F. (%) Depletion of pollutants after addition of lime and alum for paper mill effluent (System-IV)

No.	Volume of lime solution (ml)	Volume of alum solution (ml)	pH	TSS (%)	COD (%)
1.	4	6	6.5	50	40
2.	6	10	7.5	78	60
3.	10	16	7.5	88	68
4.	12	16	8.5	90	70

Table 3G. Settled sludge volume in different times after addition of lime and alum for paper mill effluent (System-IV)

No. System	Settled sludge volume in different times (ml)				
	2 min	5 min	10 min	15 min	30 min
1. 1 L sample + 4 ml lime + 6 ml alum	750	700	600	550	500
2. 1 L sample + 6 ml lime + 8 ml alum	750	700	600	500	450
3. 1 L sample + 10 ml lime + 15 ml alum	700	600	500	400	350
4. 1 L sample + 12 ml lime + 15 ml alum	600	600	450	400	350

7.5. The system was not suitable as the sludge settling rate was too slow when 10 ml lime and 15 ml alum was added and pH increased to 8.5 was not suitable for activated sludge process though % of depletion in TSS and COD was satisfactory. Another cause of discarding this system is use of excessive chemicals for achieving the desired depletion. In the System-V, (Tables 3H and 3I), it was seen that addition of polyelectrolyte with alum and lime was found more effective. Maximum depletion of pollutants load and better sludge settling rate has been observed. As main aim was to reduce the BOD load by

activated sludge process, the pH of the inlet effluent maintained around 7.5 to 8.0. Considering the above sludge the dosing of 8 ml lime, 12 ml alum and 1 ml polyelectrolyte solution per liter of effluent was selected. Coagulation/flocculation may be used as a pretreatment prior to biological treatment in order to enhance biodegradability of the waste water during biological treatment⁹. So, the essential feature of flocculation is the elimination of suspended solid and as much of the organic material as possible¹⁰. Our study was similar to the studies by NabiBidhendi *et al.*¹¹ and by Amuda and Amoo¹². Vanerkar *et al.*¹³ also reported that individually, alum did not give good results but alum with cationic polyelectrolyte in the ratio of 300 : 0.25 mg l⁻¹ resulted in the best removals of COD, BOD and suspended solids of 64.0, 69.4 and 80.82% respectively and lime with cationic polyelectrolyte in the ratio of 300 : 0.20 mg l⁻¹ with COD, BOD and suspended solids removals of 57.6, 65.1 and 74.0%, respectively. In our study, in leather effluent, COD, BOD and phenol were reduced by 95.82, 96.59 and 98.57% respectively whereas for paper effluent COD and BOD were reduced 63 and 62.34% respectively.

Biological treatment :

Biological treatment of waste water is a good method for removal of industrial effluent. Treatment of waste with bacteria involves the stabilization of waste by decomposing them into harmless inorganic solids either by aerobic or anaerobic process. Hence, aerobic treatment was accomplished to have better performance in the treatment of waste¹⁴. To start the operation, diluted mixed leather and paper waste water, the pH of which had been adjusted to 7.2 and 7.5 with COD of 6143 and 1215 mg/L respectively were introduced. In leather effluent, after 2nd stage of one day, depletions were 0.98, 0.86 and 0.30% for COD, BOD and phenol respectively. % Depletion in TSS value was also observed. In case of paper

Table 3H. (%) Depletion of pollutants after addition of lime, alum and non-ionic polyelectrolyte for paper mill effluent (System-V)

No.	Volume of lime solution (ml)	Volume of alum solution (ml)	Volume of non-ionic polyelectrolyte solution (ml)	pH	TSS (%)	COD (%)	BOD (%)
1.	4	6	1	6.5	65	45	38
2.	6	10	1	7.5	92	70	63
3.	8	12	1	7.8	95	70	65
4.	12	16	1	8.5	96	71	67

Table 3I. Settled sludge volume in different times after addition of lime, alum and non-ionic polyelectrolyte for paper mill effluent (System-V)

No. System	Settled sludge volume in different times (ml)				
	2 min	5 min	10 min	15 min	20 min
1. 1 L sample + 4 ml lime + 7 ml alum + 1 ml non-ionic polyelectrolyte	700	650	500	400	350
2. 1 L sample + 6 ml lime + 10 ml alum + 1 ml non-ionic polyelectrolyte	600	500	350	300	300
3. 1 L sample + 8 ml lime + 12 ml alum + 1 ml non-ionic polyelectrolyte	650	500	350	300	300
4. 1 L sample + 12 ml lime + 16 ml alum + 1 ml non-ionic polyelectrolyte	600	500	300	300	250

Fig. 4. Showing differences of BOD values before and after treatment for leather chemical effluent.

Fig. 4A. Showing differences of BOD values before and after treatment for paper mill effluent.

Fig. 5. Showing differences of phenol values before and after treatment for leather chemical effluent.

Fig. 6A. Showing (%) depletion of TSS in different steps for leather chemical effluent. (1) After chemical treatment, (2) after 1st stage of two days biological treatment, (3) after 2nd stage of one day biological treatment, (4) after Biopac media reactor, (5) activated carbon bed, (6) after maturation pond.

effluent, depletions were 2.25, 24.33 and 30.24% for TSS, COD and BOD respectively. Vidal *et al.*¹⁵, reported the biodegradability and toxicity of diluted leather tannery effluents waste water after being treated by an activated sludge system. Fluidized bed reactor was considered as aerobic attached growth treatment processes for leather effluent treatment plant. Rajasimman and Karthikeyan³, carried out aerobic digestion of starch industry waste water in an inverse fluidized bed bioreactor using low density polypropylene particles and reported maximum COD removal of 95.6% occurred at an organic loading rate of 1.35 kg COD/m³/d.

Tertiary treatment :

Activated carbon adsorption as the post-treatment process is necessary to further remove the remaining non-biodegradable particles¹⁶, has the BOD, COD removal

Fig. 6B. Showing (%) depletion of COD and BOD in different steps for leather chemical effluent. (1) After chemical treatment, (2) after 1st stage of two days biological treatment, (3) after 2nd stage of one day biological treatment, (4) after Biopac media reactor, (5) activated carbon bed, (6) after maturation pond.

Fig. 6C. Showing (%) depletion of phenol in different steps for leather chemical effluent. (1) After chemical treatment, (2) after 1st stage of two days biological treatment, (3) after 2nd stage of one day biological treatment, (4) after Biopac media reactor, (5) activated carbon bed, (6) after maturation pond.

efficiencies¹⁷ and can be used to remove the color, odor from waste water. In our present study, COD, BOD and phenol depletion of leather effluent obtained with activated carbon treatment were about 0.06, 0.05 and 0.11 percent respectively. Johnson *et al.*¹⁸ reported the ability of maturation pond. In leather effluent, after maturation pond, percent depletion for COD, BOD and phenol were 0.06, 0.03, 0.11 respectively.

Fig. 6D. Showing (%) depletion of TSS in different steps for paper mill effluent. (1) After physical separation, (2) after chemical treatment, (3) after biological treatment.

Fig. 6E. Showing (%) depletion of COB and BOD in different steps for paper mill effluent. (1) After physical separation, (2) after chemical treatment, (3) after biological treatment.

Conclusions :

Studies on selection of appropriate treatment techniques for industrial waste have been conducted. Physical, chemical and biological treatments were selected due to its cost-effectiveness and environmental acceptability. Tertiary treatment was also selected in case of leather effluent. From the above experiments, the best treatment process was finalized and these treatments were able to deplete the pollution load to below the permissible limit of Pollution Control Board.

So, it might be concluded from the study that chemical treatment followed by biological and tertiary treatments was the best technique for controlling pollution due to leather effluents whereas in case of paper effluent, chemical treatment including addition of lime, alum and polyelectrolyte solution in a proper dose was highly effective for removing pollutants.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the cooperation of Fanasia Ltd., Mankundu, West Bengal and Unisavo Paper Mill, Jhargram, West Bengal to carry out this study.

References

1. J. Kanagaraz, K. C. Velappan, N. K. Chandra Babu and S. Sadulla, *Journal of Scientific & Industrial Research*, 2006, **65**, 541.
2. T. Ramasami, J. R. Rao, N. K. Chandrababu, K. Parthasarathi, P. G. Rao, P. Saravanan, T. Ramasami, K. J. Sreeram and R. Gayathri, UNIDO manual on design, operational and maintenance of tannery effluent treatment plants, Unit 1 (RePo-UNIDO and AISHTMA, Chennai), 1999, 20.
3. M. Rajasimman and C. Karthikeyan, *J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manage.*, 2007, **11**, 97.
4. A. Tilman, "Pulp and Paper Pollution : The Toxic Legacy of Federal Neglect", Reach for Unbleached Foundation, Comox, BC, 2008.
5. S. J. Arceivala and S. R. Asolekar, "Waste water treatment for pollution control and reuse", 3rd ed., Tata McGraw-Hill Publishers, New Delhi, 2008.
6. S. K. Jain, M. K. Purkait, S. De and P. K. Bhattacharya, *Separation Science and Technology*, 2008, **41**, 3329.
7. D. Mishra, M. A. Khan, M. Mudgal, P. Padmakaran and B. Chakradhar, *Indian Journal of Chemical Technology*, 2009, **16**, 79.
8. I. N. Peter and S. Roy, *JSDC*, 1991, **107**, 215.
9. O. S. Amuda, I. A. Amoo and O. O. Ajayi, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2006, **B129**, 69.
10. N. Z. Al-Mutairi, M. F. Hamoda and I. Al-Ghusain, *Bioresour. Technol.*, 2004, **96**, 115.
11. G. R. NabiBidhendi, A. Torabian, H. Ehsani and N. Razmkhah, *Iran J. Environ. Health Sci. Eng.*, 2007, **4**, 29.
12. O. S. Amuda and I. A. Amoo, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2007, **141**, 778.
13. A. P. Vanerkar, S. Satyanarayan and D. M. Dharmadhikari, *Environ. Technol.*, 2005, **26**, 389.
14. B. S. N. Raju, "Water supply and waste water engineering", Tata McGraw Hill Publishers, 1995, p. 352.
15. G. Vidal, J. Nieto, K. Cooman, M. Gajardo and C. Bornhardt, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2004, **112**, 143.
16. K. Wang, S. Liu, Q. Zhang and Y. He, *Environ. Technol.*, 2009, **30**, 1469.
17. L. Malik, M. A. Al-Hashimi and M. M. Al-Doori, *Desalination*, 2007, **216**, 116.
18. M. Johnson, M. A. Camargo Valero and D. D. Mara, *Water Science & Technology*, 2007, **55**, 135.

